

Figure 3. Pick list options										
Intended Use Choices	Field of Study Choices	Exposure Choices	Data Type Choices	ToxRTool Use	Changes made to "Test Substance Identification"	Changes made to "Test System Characterization"	Changes made to "Study Design Description"	Changes made to "Study Results Documentation"	Changes made to "Plausibility of Study Design and Data"	Other changes not categorized based on the original ToxRTool 5 groups
study reliability	Toxicology	Biocides	in vitro	Followed (F)	question(s)	question(s)	question(s)	question(s)	question(s)	question(s)
study quality	Ecotoxicology	ingredients	in vivo	Modified (M)	questions with	questions with	questions with	questions with	questions with	questions with
data quality	Health	Pesticides	ex vivo	used a prior	question(s)	question(s)	question(s)	question(s)	question(s)	question(s)
data reliability	Epidemiology	Botanicals	in silico	added (A) to ToxRTool	"Criteria Group"	"Criteria Group"	"Criteria Group"	"Criteria Group"	"Criteria Group"	"Criteria Group"
study evaluation	Medical	Medical Devices	computational		scoring system	scoring system	scoring system	scoring system	scoring system	scoring system
reliability assessment	Dental	Medicinal products	other		none (not mentioned or addressed)	none (not mentioned or addressed)	none (not mentioned or addressed)	none (not mentioned or addressed)	none (not mentioned or addressed)	none (not mentioned or addressed)
quality assessment	Efficacy	feedstuff, incl.								
methodology quality	Veterinary	Nanomaterials								
only cited	other	chemicals								
risk of bias (RoB)		intervention (e.g.								
review		other								
feedback										
other										

Figure 3. Pick list options. Each column represents a field of interest with the subsequent rows outlining the possible options a reviewer can choose from. For example, in column titled 'ToxRTool Use' has four options: 1) Followed (F), 2) Modified (M), 3) Referenced and used a prior publication's modification(s), and 4) Added (A) to ToxRTool.